

Methods Of Developing The Vocabulary Of Children With Underdeveloped Speech And Testing Methodology

Surayyo Shoakhmedova

Teacher of the speech therapy department of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami

Abstract: *development of vocabulary of 4-5-year-old children based on game activities, improvement of movement, didactic exercises, text, sound, graphics, photo.*

Keywords — Children's finger exercises starting from 6-7 months, find the difference of lightly massaging the hands for 2-3 minutes, find the name of a labyrinth, text, object, draw a decoration.

INTRODUCTION.

Today's demand is to raise physically healthy, spiritually mature individuals in the society. A well-rounded generation is the guarantee of a bright future. For this reason, youth support has become one of the priority directions of our state policy.

Long-term research of scientists has shown that 70% of the knowledge that a person can acquire during his lifetime is acquired between the ages of 3 and 7. Because during this period, all cognitive processes in the child grow and develop.

In recent years, in our country, great attention has been paid to the system of pre-school education, to fundamentally improve the level of preparation of children for school education, to implement modern educational programs and technologies in the educational process, to educate children in all intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical aspects. All opportunities are being created in order to create conditions for development.

As time turned to progress and development, there was a demand to improve factors, methods, and tools that serve as effective tools in the process of education. Ten years ago, a 5-year-old boy has completely different interests, actions, and masculinity. Therefore, new methods are emerging at all stages of education.

It is known that raising a mature generation is carried out first in the family, and then in a preschool educational institution. This tradition should be continued responsibly. Based on the needs of the times, the patriots find the necessary measures and implement them into the system.

A child of preschool age has stronger visual and visual memory than auditory memory. Taking this into account, if classes are organized using games, visual aids, multimedia-didactic games, every child will feel the practical result of learning motivation, develop moral qualities, honesty, fairness, determination. The ground is created for the growth of creativity, free thinking, speech and, most importantly, keeping up with modern technologies.

The game opens wide opportunities for preschool children to learn in preschool educational institutions. In didactic

games, the learning process is directly connected with the games. Through games, including didactic games, the child begins to learn directly. Many pedagogues and psychologists have conducted and are still conducting scientific research on the issue of using games in the education of preschool children. In the process of playing the game, children's imagination and knowledge expands, the concepts and ideas formed in the child's mind are clarified.

If we comment on didactic games, it is the development of the child's range of knowledge in the form of training with children in the form of special educational games. Didactic games are both a game and an educational tool. In the process of such a game, the child develops all mental processes and forms individual characteristics.

Developing the cognitive process of preschool children using multimedia-didactic games is one of the most effective ways recognized in the world today. Multimedia - use of modern technical and software tools. It consists of interactive visual and audio effects under the control of interactive software, which combines text, sound, graphics, photos, video in a digital presentation.

Another advantage of training using multimedia-didactic games is that there is no compulsory education in such an organized training. The child accepts knowledge voluntarily, and through this the educator achieves a positive result.

The use of multimedia-didactic games helps the child to enter school with confidence and enthusiasm for the future. Over the years, the value of gold has increased, but not decreased. Indeed, knowledge acquired in youth is as priceless as a pattern carved in stone.

What games help the child's speech development?

Scientists have proven that the development of speech and thinking of young children is directly proportional to the number and shape of fine movements of hands and fingers.

Children with highly developed finger movement skills have better speech, thinking, memory, and attention. A child's speech development cannot be achieved until the movements of the fingers are free. It is necessary to start working on finger exercises in children from the age of 6-7 months. It is necessary to gently massage the hands for 2-3 minutes every day.

Stimulating hand exercises consist of 5 stages:

1. rub the child's hand 8-10 times from the outside to the elbow;
2. bend and straighten the fingers 5-6 times (except for the thumb) 5-6 times;
3. bend the thumb to the right and left, move it in a circle;
4. activate the palm 2-3 times: stroking the middle of the child's palm with a finger in a slow spiral, the spiral expands and ends at the child's thumb;
5. rub the child's hand 8-10 times from the outside to the elbow.

Exercises that develop fine movements of the fingers:

- *starting from the age of ten months, all the fingers of the child should be involved in the movement - putting together and placing cubes, pyramids, hemispheres of different sizes.*
- *from one to one and a half years old, making wooden or plastic toys, for example, making pyramids and houses from Legos;*
- *collecting all kinds of shapes from mosaics in the period from one and a half to two years old;*
- *at the age of two to three years old, to string toys and large buttons in a row by passing a rope through the holes, to make ties of various shapes from the ropes;*
- *articulation exercises: blowing up balloons, trying to pronounce words piece by piece.*

By performing various exercises with fingers, children develop fine finger movements, which not only has a beneficial effect on the development of speech, but also prepares the child to draw and write.

Attention games for children

When a child is still small, his neglect is not a concern, but as he grows up, it becomes more difficult for him to live. "The first call" worries parents when the child starts kindergarten, but serious problems arise when he goes to elementary school. A small child is often distracted in classes, forgets to write down the assignment, does not listen to the teacher's lesson, these difficulties grow like a pile of snow. At home they kill him at first. then they start fighting. But this is not a way out of the situation. The child is not to blame for such anxiety, moreover, he cannot solve this problem alone.

Find the difference

Various objects are placed on the table and the child must remember the names of these objects. Then the child turns around and the leader of the game changes the place of the objects or takes something away. The child must find what has changed on the table.

Find the name of the object

This game can be played anywhere - at home, on a walk, on the way to school or kindergarten. The child is asked to find an object of a certain shape, color, made of any specified material, or whose name begins with a given letter.

Decorative drawing

Any decoration is drawn using colored pencils, and then the child is allowed to finish the picture. By the way, instead of decoration, you can use mosaic or simple colored sticks.

Labyrinth

Who doesn't love a maze? Arrange a small adventure for the little one, let him go through the drawn maze with his eyes, if he has difficulty with it, let him go through it with a pencil.

Text

Take any newspaper or magazine and ask them to delete a letter, for example J or R, from the given text. In this case, it is better if you set a time and let him move in a row.

Examples or problems can also be solved (not necessarily from the school curriculum) - it is very interesting if the whole family participates in the mathematical process. The main thing is to give the training a competitive spirit. The child gradually learns to concentrate while solving verbal mathematical solutions. Start with the easiest tasks first and then make them more difficult. It will be more effective if you emphasize your child's achievements and reward him in this process.

In addition to all this, rebuses, board games, chess or checkers also improve visual memory - it also improves concentration and thinking.

References

- [1] Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the Strategy of Actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. // Towards rapid development and renewal based on the strategy of actions. - T.: Gafur Ghulam publishing house, 2017. - P.70-71.
- [2] Z.M. Ahmedova, M.Yu. Ayupova, M.P. Khamidova. Logopedic home. Tashkent-2013.
- [3] Abidova, N. (2022). Problems of Preparing Future Defectologists to Work in the Conditions of Inclusive Education. Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results, 2505-2511.
- [4] Abidova, N. (2021). Organization Of The Work Of The Logo Teacher With Children With Disabilities In The Conditions Of Inclusive Preschool Practice. Turkish Journal of Physiotherapy and Rehabilitation, 33382-33398.
- [5] Abidova, N. Z. (2013). Peculiarities of the Formation and Development of Vocabulary in Children with Vision Disorders. European Researcher, (2-3), 475-479.